

A STUDY OF EARLY PREDICTION OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS IN BRIDGES

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Annotation. *As civil engineering structures are growing in dimension and longevity, there is an associated increase in concern regarding the maintenance of such structures. Bridges, in particular, are critical links in today's transportation networks and hence fundamental for the development of society. In this context, the demand for novel damage detection techniques and reliable structural health monitoring systems is currently high. This paper presents a model-free damage detection approach based on machine learning techniques. The method is applied to data on the structural condition of a fictitious railway bridge gathered in a numerical experiment using a three-dimensional finite element model. Data are collected from the dynamic response of the structure, which is simulated in the course of the passage of a train, considering the bridge in healthy and two different damaged scenarios. In the first stage of the proposed method, artificial neural networks are trained with an unsupervised learning approach with input data composed of accelerations gathered on the healthy bridge. Based on the acceleration values at previous instants in time, the networks are able to predict future accelerations. In the second stage, the prediction errors of each network are statistically characterized by a Gaussian process that supports the choice of a damage detection threshold. Subsequent to this, by comparing damage indices with said threshold, it is possible to discriminate between different structural conditions, namely between healthy and damaged. From here and for each damage case scenario, receiver operating characteristic curves that illustrate the trade-off between true and false positives can be obtained. Lastly, based on the Bayes'*

Theorem, a simplified method for the calculation of the expected total cost of the proposed strategy, as a function of the chosen threshold, is suggested.

Keywords: Structural health monitoring, Damage detection, Model-free-based method, Artificial neural networks, Statistical model development, Receiver operating characteristic curve, Bayes' theorem, Probability-based expected cost.

1.Introduction. The present time is without doubt the most appropriate for the development of robust and reliable structural damage detection systems as ageing civil engineering structures, such as bridges, are being used past their life expectancy and well beyond their original design loads. Often, when a significant damage to the structure is discovered, the deterioration has already progressed far, and required repair work is substantial and costly. Seldom will the structure be demolished and a new one constructed in its place. This entails substantial expenditures and has negative impact on the environment and traffic during replacement. The ability to monitor a structure in real-time and detect damage at the earliest possible stage supports clever maintenance strategies and provides accurate remaining life predictions. For the exposed reasons, the demand for such smart structural health monitoring (SHM) systems is currently high.

The existing methods implemented in damage detection can be essentially divided into model-based and model-free. The first approach presupposes an accurate finite element model of the target structure, following that one obvious advantage of this approach is that the damage detected has a direct physical interpretation. Yet, it may be difficult to develop an accurate model of a complex structure and it can be intricate as well to obtain and update the parameters defining the structure. On the contrary, the model-free approach allows circumventing the problem of having to develop a precise structural model, mostly by means of artificial intelligence, but it is more difficult to assign a physical meaning to the detected damage. The model-free approach consists in training an algorithm on some acquired data, usually in an unsupervised manner, so that at the end it is able

to tell apart different condition states of the structure. These algorithms are referred to as outlier or novelty detection methods: if there are significant deviations between measured and expected values, the algorithm is said to indicate novelty, meaning that the structure has departed from its normal condition and is probably damaged.

This paper presents a model-free damage detection approach based on artificial neural networks. The method is applied to data gathered from simulations of train passages on the finite element model of a fictitious railway bridge. The data sets are obtained from one healthy and two damage case scenarios of the bridge. This data would in reality be obtained directly from measurements performed on the real structure of interest, without the need to develop a complex numerical model. In the first stage of the proposed method, artificial neural networks are trained in an unsupervised manner with input data composed of gathered accelerations on the healthy bridge. Based on the acceleration values at previous instants in time, the networks are able to predict future accelerations. In the second stage, the prediction errors of each network are statistically characterized by a Gaussian process that supports the choice of a damage detection threshold. Then, by comparing damage indices with the threshold, the system is able to point out damage on the bridge. To evaluate the performance of the system, receiver operating characteristic curves that illustrate the trade-off between true and false positives are generated. Finally, based on the Bayes' theorem, a simplified method for the calculation of the expected total cost of the proposed strategy, as a function of the chosen threshold, is suggested.

2.Literature review. A review of some of the most recent developments within SHM and damage detection that resulted in published articles in scientific peer-reviewed journals is here presented. Regarding optimal sensor placement (OSP), a crucial part of any damage detection system, mention can be made to the work of Huang et al. [1] using genetic algorithms, where the proposed algorithm uses the sensor types as input and criteria about the desired measurement accuracy

to deliver the optimal number of sensors and their location. The method was validated with experimental analysis on a single-bay steel frame structure case study. Liet al. [2] proposed a novel approach termed dual-structure coding and mutation particle swarm optimization (DSC- MPSO) algorithm. Using a numerical example of a three- span pre-stressed concrete cable-stayed bridge, this approach was demonstrated to have increased convergence speed and precision when compared to the other state-of- the-art methods (e.g. genetic algorithm). Still within the OSP topic, Yi et al. [3] proposed a new optimal sensor placement technique in multi-dimensional space since most available procedures for sensor placement only guarantee optimization in an individual structural direction, which results in an ineffective optimization of the sensing net- work when employing multi-axial sensors. A numerical study was conducted on a benchmark structure model.

Another common topic of research is the separation of the changes in structural response caused by operational and environmental variability from the changes triggered by damage. This is indeed one of the principal challenges to transit SHM technology from research to practice. Jin et al. [4] proposed an extended Kalman filter-based artificial neural network for damage detection in a highway bridge under severe temperature changes. The time-lagged natural frequencies, time-lagged temperature and season index are selected as the inputs for the neural network, which predicts the natural frequency at the next time step. The Kalman filter is used to estimate the weights of the neural network and the confidence intervals of the natural frequencies that allow for damage detection. The method was tested with a numerical case study of an existing bridge. The published work regarding machine learning methods applied in SHM is continuously expanding.

Machine learning algorithms have been implemented to expose structural abnormalities from monitoring data. These algorithms normally belong to the outlier detection category, which considers training data coming exclusively from the normal condition of the structure (unsupervised learning). Worden and Farrar [5]

have contributed with reputable work on monitoring of structures using machine learning techniques, such as neural networks, genetic algorithms, and support vector machines. Rao and Lakshmi [6] proposed a novel damage identification technique combining proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) with time-frequency analysis using Hilbert Huang transform (HHT) and dynamic quantum particle swarm optimization (DQPSO). The algorithm was tested with two numerical examples with single and multiple damages. Diezetal. [7] proposed a Clustering-based data-driven machine learning approach, using the k - mean clustering algorithm, to group joints with similar behavior on the bridge to separate the ones working in normal condition from the ones working in abnormal condition. The feasibility of the approach was demonstrated using data collected during field test measurements of the Sydney Harbour Bridge. Zhou et al. [8] proposed a structural damage detection method based on posteriori probability support vector machine (PPSVM) and Dempster-Shafer (DS) evidence theory adopted to combine the decision level fusion information. The proposed damage detection method was verified by means of experimental analysis of a benchmark structure model. All the mentioned latter combined methods revealed to improve the accuracy and stability of the damage detection system when compared to other popular data mining methods.

There are several published works regarding the detection of structural damage with the aid of Machine Learning techniques. Still, most of the proposed methods are based on a supervised learning approach, which requires data of the damage condition of the structure to be available. This poses a difficulty to the practical implementation of these methods because, as it is known, the data in damaged condition does not normally exist. The method presented in this paper consists in an updated mode-free damage detection algorithm using Machine Learning techniques based on the work of Gonzalez [9]. The primary step in this study involves the development of a three-dimensional finite element model of a railway bridge. The

vertical deck accelerations at different positions of the bridge are gathered using simulations of train passages and assuming that the bridge behaves in both normal and abnormal conditions, considering one baseline model and two damaged models, respectively. The first stage of the proposed method consists in the design and training of artificial neural networks (ANNs) which, given any input features, are trained to predict future values of the features. Following the validation of the best trained network, the second stage of the proposed algorithm consists in using the predicted acceleration errors to fit a Gaussian process (GP) that enables to perform a statistical analysis of the errors' distributions. After this process, damage indices (DIs) can be obtained and compared to a defined detection threshold for the system, allowing for one to study the probability of true and false detection events. From these results, a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve is generated and used to obtain information about the performance of the algorithm. Finally, a simplified method for the calculation of the expected total cost of the strategy based on the Bayes' Theorem is proposed.

3. Background in SHM. Visual inspections are regarded as the basic technique for the assessment of condition of in-service bridges, as this technique is intuitive and provides information in a direct way exclusively based on observation. However, this technique used alone has many shortcomings due to the growing complexity in the design of modern structures. One can mention as disadvantages the fact that the technique may not be practicable if the structure has restricted accessibility or if the traffic is excessively disturbed, its application is time-discrete and the conclusion of the visual inspection is inevitably subjective. In this sense, effort was placed in developing damage detection techniques that handle measurement data to find structural changes [10].

Structural health monitoring techniques comprise non- physically and physically based methods. The former uses a system model to study a physical structure and predict the responses; examples of methods that fall into this category

are the probabilistic, non-parametric and autoregressive models (AR) methods [11]. The physically based methods perform damage identification by comparing natural frequencies and mode shapes data between the healthy and damaged structural model [12]; examples of methods that fall into this category are the vibration-based damage identification methods (VBDIM), such as frequency response [13], mode shape and strain energy methods [14], modal flexibility and modal stiffness methods. Many broad classes of damage detection algorithms have emerged, most dealing with vibration measurements and modal analysis of the structural system. Although structural properties like damping, modal shapes and frequencies are not directly measurable, they can be inferred from other measured data. These properties have somewhat clear definitions and allow the relatively easy design of algorithms that define them, therefore being good candidates for parameters of a damage detection technique.

Damage identification is far from being a forthright process, from the basic step of defining what damage is up to decoding it in mathematical terms. Due to the random variability in experimentally measured dynamic response data, statistical approaches are desired to make sure that the perceived changes in the structure's response are coming from existing damage and not from variations in the operational and environmental conditions. The careful integration of recent sensing technology with traditional inspection and avant-garde diagnostic techniques will provide essential information that engineers and policy-makers need to manage the structures that serve our society.

4. Performance of a classifier. The damage detection process concerning civil engineering structures involves a significant amount of uncertainty, which can determine whether damage is discovered or not. The uncertainties can stem from many causes but are generally due to [15,16]: inaccuracy in the FEM discretization; uncertainties in geometry and boundary conditions; non-linearity in material properties, environmental settings (e.g. variations in temperature and traffic); errors

associated with measurements (e.g. noise) and signal post-processing techniques. The consequences of false detection can be more or less stern and it is, thus, imperative to carefully investigate the sources of uncertainties, quantify and control their influence. The analysis of Type I (false positive) and Type II (false negative) errors is a frequent practice of reporting the performance of a binary classification, where there are four possible outcomes (Table 1) from an inspection event in a structure. Two statistical tools that enable the evaluation of these errors, in terms of unwanted results (false positives and negatives) and desired results (true positives and negatives), are the probability of detection (POD) curve [17,18] and the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve [19,20], the latter used in this paper. A ROC curve is a two-dimensional graphic in which the true positive rate (TPR) is plotted against the false positive rate (FPR) for a given threshold. The graphic demonstrates thus relative trade-offs between benefits and costs, respectively, TPR and FPR, depending on a threshold that is selected[21,22]. A very high (strict) threshold will never indicate damage since the classifier finds no positives, resulting in 0% of false and true positives, whereas a very low (lenient) threshold will always indicate damage since everything is classified positive, resulting in 100% of false and true positives. One common way to define the best threshold is by fixing an acceptable FPR and then trying to maximize the TPR. The ROC curve provides a tool for cost-benefit analysis assisting the practitioner in the selection among different available classifiers and their detection threshold. The optimal detection threshold will commonly be the one that minimizes the total expected cost, which will be connected with the odds of false detection. The accepted idea is that one point in the ROC space is considered better than another if it is associated with a higher TPR for the same FPR[23]. The closer the curve is to the left and top borders of the ROC space, resembling an inverted L shape, the superior the performance of the classifier; the closer the curve is to a 45° diagonal in the ROC space, the less accurate is the classifier.

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